

Ageing and Productivity: A Cross-Country Analysis of the Effects of Ageing Workforce on Economic Performance

Abstract

This study uses a strongly balanced panel dataset on 13 OECD member countries. The effects of an ageing population are analyzed on the productivity of the economies, which is captured and measured by their annual GDP growth in percentage. The period studied is 25 years from 1996-2021.

I have used two economic theories; Lifecycle Hypothesis (LCH) (Modigliani, 1966) and Social Identity and self-categorization (Tajfel et al., 1979) to aid in my research. These theories provide a solid, starting framework for my model in selecting and justifying the variables, that describes the relationship between an ageing economy and their work performance. Social Identity Theory (Tajfel et al., 1979) suggests that individuals at work categorize themselves based on shared characteristics which can influence their behaviors and attitudes towards work and retirement. Whereas, LCH (Modigliani, 1966) suggests that individuals adjust their saving and consumption patterns over a period of time, based on their expected income trajectory. This can influence economic productivity, as these patterns change the overall demand and supply of goods and services.

The results showed several demographic factors, which are significant when analyzing the effects of an ageing population on economic growth. Indicators such as inflation, Human development index (HDI), urbanization growth rate, fertility rates, labor force participation, life expectancy, and imports, all significantly impacted the economy. Pension spending was also found to have a negative correlation with growth, however, its magnitude as it currently stands was quite low. HDI had the highest positive impact on growth, approximately 225.1%, which impacted growth positively whereas, the fertility rate had a negative impact on growth, approximately 10.4%. Other factors such as the median age of the population, unemployment rates, and the GINI index were found to be statistically insignificant. The results of the Hausman test suggested a fixed effects model was the most appropriate estimation technique for this cross-country analysis. The software used to perform all the statistical analysis was done on STATA MP version 17.0

Keywords: Low Fertility Rates, Ageing Population, Productivity, Inflation

Introduction

Technological advancement has changed our world rapidly, and in this ever-growing fast-paced global economy, have arisen some issues that cannot be ignored. If negated now, the global economy could crash very rapidly in the future. Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, cross-border trade has grown worldwide 20-fold since the 1950s and the cross-border financial flows have increased by nearly 200 times since the '70s (IMF, 2021).

One of the most significant challenges, the rapid advancement has brought is, the ageing population in developed economies. If there are no changes made in the policies or behavior, the ratio of working-age individuals to those aged over 65 caused by population ageing would create a significant challenge in welfare and public funding pensions and social security (Disney, 1997). There may be a risk of a shortage of workers in certain industries and occupations as the labor market may require the services of more youthful employees (Disney, 1997).

Japan, one of the most highly developed countries in the world, is also facing the highest ageing population in its economy. According to (Bank, 2022) Japan's population that is 65 and above has reached 30% in the year 2021. The major causes for Japan's ageing economy are multifaceted and they include low fertility rates which had fallen to 1.29 children per woman in 2003 (Retherford and Ogawa, 2005). These were caused by delayed marriages and childbearing due to changes in social norms and economic conditions, including a higher participation rate of women in higher education (Retherford and Ogawa, 2005). Japan could likely encounter a wide range of problems soon due to its shifts and allocating support resources for a rapidly growing elderly population. Male life expectancy at birth had reached 78.4, and female life expectancy had reached 85.3 by 2003, the highest in the world (Ogawa, 2005).

This demographic shift has important implications for economic performance and productivity, as older workers tend to have different skills, abilities, physical strength, and work preferences than younger workers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the extent to which demographic factors, such as age distribution and retirement patterns, affect economic productivity in different countries. Specifically, I will examine the relationship between, the ageing workforce, and economic performance across a range of countries using a cross-country analysis. My research will contribute to the existing literature on the subject, by providing insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with an ageing workforce and its impact on economic productivity.

The research question that I wish to explore is: To what extent do demographic factors, such as age distribution and retirement patterns, affect economic productivity in different countries? By answering this question, I hope to inform policymakers, businesses, and other stakeholders about the implications of an ageing workforce for economic performance and devise strategies that may be needed to address these challenges.

1. Theoretical perspectives

In this section, I will be discussing some of the theories in economics relating to older workers present in the labor force, productivity, and growth implications of an ageing economy.

1.1 Social Identity and self-categorization theories

According to (Tajfel et al., 1979) individuals categorize themselves and others into social groups based on shared characteristics such as race, gender, nationality, religion, etc. So, based on perceived similarities, individuals tend to identify more strongly with their groups and view other members of the groups as less favorable. This, however, can lead to an intergroup conflict. When groups compete for resources and status, or when there are perceived threats to the ingroup's identity or values (Tajfel et al., 1979). But this conflict can be mitigated via strategies that involve contact between the groups, promoting common goals and organizational values, and emphasizing a shared identity rather than focusing on differences (Tajfel et al., 1979).

While age is an important social identity that holds the potential to affect economic outcomes, older workers are less likely to be called back for job interviews than younger workers with similar qualifications (Neumark et al., 2017). (Fiske et al., 2007) research has shown that age-based stereotypes and discrimination can lead to unequal treatment at the workplace, i.e., these could include, reduced compensation and limited chances for career advancement. Additionally, older workers may face multiple challenges in finding employment due to age-related biases. This causes serious implications for the economic outcomes of older workers, leading to lower employment and lower earnings (Neumark et al., 2017).

Lower earnings mean, that older workers are more likely to be stuck in low-paying jobs with limited prospects for progress. They may also be more vulnerable to wage discrimination. This results in their financial insecurity and well-being (Johnson, 2009). One major reason for this disparity is, older people face discrimination from employers who assume they are less productive or less capable than younger workers. This notion can also lead to lower pay and fewer opportunities for promotion, even if older workers have the same qualifications and experience as their younger counterparts (Neumark et al., 2017). However, in the context of age discrimination during hiring, the strategies proposed by (Tajfel et al., 1979) social identity theory could potentially be applied to reduce biases and stereotypes about older workers. One example that comes to mind and is very applicable to mitigate this situation is to increase the social contract between the older and younger generation groups by having mentorship programs and team-building activities to promote a greater understanding and bonding between the two groups.

Another study (Ng and Feldman, 2008) found that older workers tend to have lower levels of creativity compared to younger workers. This very well could be, a huge shortcoming, especially in fields that require a high degree of innovation and problem-solving. On the other

hand, though, it was also noted that older workers tend to have higher levels of organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs) compared to younger workers. OCBs are considered voluntary tasks that contribute to the overall functioning of an organization, such as helping coworkers or going above and beyond job requirements. This is seen as an advantage, especially in fields that value teamwork and collaboration (Ng and Feldman, 2008).

On the issues of absenteeism and punctuality, the results were mixed when comparing older and younger workers. Some studies showed that older workers had lower rates of absenteeism and tardiness compared to younger workers, while others showed no significant difference at all. This may very well be dependent on employers who are concerned about attendance and punctuality (Ng and Feldman, 2008).

1.2 Life-Cycle Hypothesis: Implications for Economic Productivity in an Ageing Workforce

Several implications can be inferred from the framework of the LCH theory. Studies show that changes in the age, of the overall population structure may exert a significant influence on economic growth. This suggests that demographic factors such as age distribution can have a significant impact on economic productivity (Bloom et al., 2010). Another point of significance is that the consumption ratio tends to be higher for the youth and the elderly, but lower for the working-age adults. This highlights, how different age groups have different economic needs, which can affect key drivers of economic growth such as labor supply, productivity, consumption, and savings in the economy (Bloom et al., 2010).

Labor supply and savings are also higher among working-age adults than those who are aged 60 or above. This suggests that the age structure of the population can affect labor supply and savings rates, which are important drivers of economic growth (Bloom et al., 2010). Also, “If age-specific behavior concerning labor supply and savings were fixed, labor supply and savings per capita would tend to decline with a rising elderly share of the population. Keeping all other factors such as productivity and migration equal, would imply lower growth in income per capita” (Bloom et al., 2010). Some experts believe that global aging may engulf the world economy and even threaten democracy itself if the situation is not rectified (Peterson, 1999). Others have stated an even more gloomy picture where the world could be overwhelmed by a self-centered generation who will suck down all the resources of the economy (Dychtwald, 1999). Overall, the effect of an ageing population on growth can have a significant impact, based on two key aspects, labor supply, and human capital accumulation (Bloom et al., 2010).

2. Literature Review

In this section, I will discuss the relevant literature and shed light on the issues of an aging workforce, its effects on productivity, and policies to tackle issues that may arise.

2.1 Macroeconomic Implications of an ageing population and policy responses

There are several key issues linked to an ageing population. It raises concerns about the financial stability/security of the elderly people in the economy, health care expenditure, tax revenues, availability of the workforce, and savings (Bloom et al., 2015). This study claims that population ageing's impact on macroeconomic performance is greatly exaggerated, as it is more feasible to compensate for behavioral changes and policy interventions. The authors also claim that the declining fertility rate has not yet had a negative impact in terms of economic growth because it is offset by the fact now more women are available to participate in the labor market. So, by increasing human capital investments in children, it can decrease the dependency on youth (Bloom et al., 2015).

So even though, the research suggests that population ageing may lead to lower rates of labor force participation and productivity, which could, in turn, reduce economic growth and tax revenues. However, the authors also note that these negative effects may be mitigated by countervailing behavioral changes and policy responses (Bloom et al., 2015). Some of the policies the study mentions are; 'delaying the retirement age, redesigning pension finance, slowing the growth of benefits, investing in education and training and increased workforce participation from women, immigrants, and older people'. Delaying the retirement age could help increase the labor force participation rate of older workers, which can help to offset the decline in the working-age population resulting from population ageing. This will ultimately reduce the burden on public finances and increase tax revenues. Redesigning the pension finance will make it more sustainable and viable in case of demographic changes. Investing in human capital and education will boost productivity and garner economic growth. And, lastly, when a larger pool of the population including, immigrants, women, and older people are participating in contributing to the economy, not only will this policy serve to reduce discrimination against these group types of workers, but it will also create a more work-life balance (Bloom et al., 2015).

2.2 Ageing Populations (OECD): Economic Effects and Implications for Public Finance

This study explores the demographic changes, declining fertility rates, and increasing life expectancy prove to be a leading cause in the ageing structure of the populations in OECD countries (Hagemann and Nicoletti, 1989). It notes there could be a substantial strain on the

economy, including high demand for healthcare and social services, shifts in savings and investment behavior in the long run, and reduced labor force participation rates. To address these challenges, governments and stakeholders would require implementing a wide range of policies if the aim is to promote economic growth. These include increasing and improving the labor force participation rates among older workers, which would ensure the sustainability of public finances. Increasing the retirement age could help mitigate this issue, for example, the normal age of retirement is being gradually increased from 65-67 for social security benefits (Hagemann and Nicoletti, 1989).

Another policy mentioned also suggests encouraging more immigration, which could help offset the negative effects of an ageing population on the labor force. Especially, skilled introducing skilled immigrants to an economy can have positive consequences on public finances by increasing the number of workers to retirees (Hagemann and Nicoletti, 1989). However, the study does not limit the immigration policy to skilled employment only. Some countries may benefit from workers with no skill requirement; though, it fails to mention any names of the countries. Lastly, they discuss about reforms in the pension system, particularly in Sweden in the 90s which involved a shift defined benefit to a defined contribution system. This reduced the generosity of pensions and incentives for workers to work longer. This partly addressed, some of the challenges posed by the ageing population phenomena (Hagemann and Nicoletti, 1989).

2.3 Population ageing and inflation

This study offers insights into the effect of inflation due to an ageing population. It studies panel data of 32 OECD member countries from 1971-2015. The results reveal that an increased old-age dependency ratio lowers the inflation rate. It mentions that Japan to become the oldest country in the sample of 32 whose population's median age would be the highest by 2050 (Broniatowska, 2019). It also mentions Korea to be the youngest country in terms of its old age population to be reported as 13.1% in 1971. But it is predicted to be at 37.4% by 2050. Overall, the results of this study concur with previous empirical findings that explain the ageing population to be negatively correlated with inflation. The reason is, as the size of the population of elderly people grow larger in an economy, savings level rise as older people tend to spend less money on goods and services. This, in turn, reduces the demand for goods and services, leading to a decrease in labor force participation, further reducing the inflation in an economy (Broniatowska, 2019).

2.4 The Impact of Population Aging and Public Health Support on EU Labor Markets

This study shows that, as the population ages, it has a negative impact on the labor market performance. The reason is, there are fewer people of working age available to the economy to take part in the labor force. Thus, this leads to a labor shortage, which in turn leads to reduced

output and productivity. Additionally, older workers may face age discrimination at workplaces due to health concerns and their ability to perform their tasks at work. The countries analyzed in this study are the 28 European Union Member States (EUMS) (Cristea et al., 2020). Their second finding regarding public health expenditure shows, a positive correlation between an ageing economy and public health. The reason for that is, as the population age increases, the demand for health care and long-term care services also goes up. This puts a strain on public finances as health expenditures are less for people who are younger and healthier than those who are older and retired (Cristea et al., 2020).

The study suggests resolving this problem, and adopting preventive approaches to healthy ageing is the first step to improving the overall health status of the population. This is achieved by promoting awareness campaigns with the help of medical professionals for the elderly. Investing in community programs, to assist older individuals could also help minimize the problem (Cristea et al., 2020).

3. Data & Methodology

In this section, I will list the sources used to collect my data and share the appropriate statistical methods used to determine the effects ageing population on productivity.

3.1 Data sources

Data for this analysis were taken from multiple and credible sources, such as the World Bank (WB), United Nations Development Program (UNDP), International Monetary Fund (IMF), and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (please see the appendix at the end for greater detail). The table on the next page shows descriptive statistics of my dataset (Please note that four of the independent variables have missing values. Total observations are 338 and the missing values will be imputed when the estimation on the model is performed).

Table 1

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Description
ADR	338	50.558	5.128	40.249	71.119	Age dependency ratio (% of working-age population)
CPI	338	94.787	16.237	49.224	127.258	Consumer price index
EXP	338	43.184	18.986	9.316	86.604	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP)
FRT	325	1.422	.161	1.09	1.87	Fertility rate, total (births per woman)
dGDP	338	2.09	3.865	-14.839	13.05	GDP growth (annual %)
std_GDPc	338	25071.279	13146.055	2327.435	53772.793	GDP per capita (current US\$)
GINI	218	31.888	3.919	23.7	39	GINI index
std_HDI	338	.864	.047	.711	.948	Human Development Index
IMP	338	43.828	18.134	8.32	84.552	Imports of goods and services (% of GDP)
LFPR	312	71.507	4.356	58.25	79.82	Labor force participation rate, total (% of total population ages 15-64)
LXB	338	78.407	3.581	68.933	84.784	Life expectancy at birth
MAGE	338	40.263	2.881	33.374	48.361	The median age of the population
PEN	310	9.728	2.916	0	17.45	Pension spending (public spending % of GDP)
UNEM	338	9.154	4.836	2.01	27.47	Unemployment, total (% of the total labor force)
dUPG	338	.22	.819	-2.282	2.283	Urban population growth (annual %)

3.2 Methodology

Based on the theoretical perspectives (Modigliani, 1966, Tajfel et al., 1979) and the literature discussed (Hagemann and Nicoletti, 1989, Bloom et al., 2015, Broniatowska, 2019, Cristea et al., 2020), my dependent variable is GDP growth (annual%) which measures the productivity of an ageing workforce. So, the equation for my model is:

$$dGDP_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ADR_{i,t} + \beta_2 CPI_{i,t} + \beta_3 EXP_{i,t} + \beta_4 IFRT_{i,t} + \beta_5 std_GDPc_{i,t} + \beta_6 IGINI_{i,t} + \beta_7 + std_HDI_{i,t} \\ + \beta_8 IMP_{i,t} + \beta_9 + ILFPR_{i,t} + \beta_{10} LXB_{i,t} + \beta_{11} MAGE_{i,t} + \beta_{12} IPEN_{i,t} + \beta_{13} UNEM_{i,t} \\ + \beta_{14} dUPG_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \mu_{i,t}$$

Using the Hausman test, I will compare which estimation technique is more appropriate, either the fixed or the random effects for my panel data analysis. These estimations assist in controlling for omitted variable bias (OVB) due to unobserved heterogeneity (Wooldridge, 2010). What is unobserved heterogeneity, one may ask? Unobserved heterogeneity refers to differences across units being studied, in my case countries. Since I have a sample of 13 countries no one country is, the same. There could be similarities between them, but they are unique entities, and things that set them apart could be the culture, language, variety of food, land size, weather, and so on. So, when studying for a larger sample size and being able to draw inferences that could fit a model generally, unobserved heterogeneities are to be accounted for otherwise the results could lead to biases.

The unobserved specific effects could be eliminated by using a fixed effects model. To demonstrate an example from a small sample of my equation, consider the effect of per capita income (current US\$) on productivity (annual GDP growth in %). The general equation for the model could be written as:

$$Y_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \mu_{i,t}$$

Where Y denotes annual GDP growth in % and X denotes per capita income (current US\$). The subscript i denotes the individual (in my case a country) and t denotes the time period. The term α_i denotes unobserved individual specific effect, i.e., something related to the individual which is not accounted for in the model but is time-invariant, and $\mu_{i,t}$ is the error term. Now, to get rid of the unobserved effect, we will take the average value of annual Y for a given individual across time period t . That gives us the mean value of our dependent variable Y and independent variable X. Since, α_i is time invariant, it remains as α_i . To get rid of the unobserved effect, we subtract averaged values from the original equation, which cancels out α_i the unobserved effects. One assumption about the fixed effect model is that individual-specific effects are correlated with the regressors in our model. If the error term is not correlated with the independent variables, we use the random effect model (Wooldridge, 2010).

3.3 Results

My dependent variable is dGDP, which is measured as the annual % growth of GDP. To determine which estimation best fits my model, I run the Hausman test to examine the consistency of the fixed vs random effects estimators (Greene, 2012). The p-value of the Hausman test was 0.00, which suggests that we reject the null hypothesis, and a fixed effects estimation is more appropriate for our model. Table 2 on the next page shows the estimated results.

Table 2

Fixed Effects Estimation	Number of observations	Standard Errors	Number of Countries	R-squared Overall	Significance
Variables	338		13	27.29%	
dGDP	Coefficient		t-values	p> t-values	
ADR	-0.0289502	0.069	-0.42	.674	***
CPI	-0.200175	0.039	-5.57	0	
EXP	-0.0239192	0.061	-0.39	.695	**
std_GDPc	-1.396035	0.587	-2.38	.018	**
std_HDI	2.250891	0.933	2.41	.016	***
IMP	0.3234292	0.071	4.52	0	**
LXB	0.7875795	0.341	2.31	.022	
MAGE	-0.3050668	0.203	-1.51	.133	
UNEM	-0.1108692	0.069	-1.60	.111	**
dUPG	0.743415	0.362	2.05	.041	***
IFRT	-0.1040843	0.011	-9.51	0	
IGINI	-0.02819	0	-1.00	.319	***
ILFPR	0.0016359	0	5.50	0	**
IPEN	-0.0033541	0.002	-2.08	.038	
Constant	-31.689	24.263	-1.31	.192	

In the fixed effects estimation, it is assumed that individual-specific effects are correlated with the independent variables which can be identified by doing the Hausman test. The R^2 describes 27.29% of the variation in my dependent variable is explained by the regressors in my model. According to the results, CPI, std_GDPc, std_HDI, IMP, LXB, dUPG, IFRT, ILFPR, and IPEN are all significant. One unit increase in CPI decreases the growth rate by, 0.02 units or 2%. One unit increase in per capita income decreases the growth rate by 1.39 units. Now, at first glance, this seems counterintuitive, but some studies have shown that if the population is decreasing while GDP remains stable or increases slightly, then GDP per capita would increase but overall GDP growth would decrease. This supports the idea of the "catch-up effect," which suggests that countries with lower initial levels of GDP tend to grow faster than those with higher initial levels (Cheng, 2011). However, it's important to note that this negative relationship between GDP per capita and economic growth is not straightforward and requires further investigation.

Also, one unit increase in the Human development index increases the growth rate by 2.25 units and is highly significant, as one would expect. LXB (Life expectancy at birth) has a positive coefficient of 0.787, which suggests that longer life expectancies tend to be associated with higher GDP growth rates. An increase in (IFRT) fertility rate also suggests that growth decreases by 0.104 units. However, it is important to note that correlation does not necessarily imply causation and other factors may also be at play. So, deeper research and analysis would be necessary to establish a causal relationship between fertility rate and GDP growth as well. dUPG (Urban population growth annual %) is positively correlated with growth and is significant as well. This means that urbanization may be contributing positively to economic growth in the sample. The last two variables that are significant are ILFPR (Labor force participation rate) and IPEN (public spending % of GDP). The positive correlation between the labor force and growth means

that higher labor force participation rates mean more people are employed and producing goods and services, leading to higher GDP growth. And a negative correlation has been found between (public spending % of GDP) as expected because higher pension spending reduces the number of resources available for investment and other productive uses, leading to lower GDP growth.

The other variables ADR(Age-dependency ratio) MAGE (Median age of population), UNEM (Unemployment, total (% of total labor force)), and IGINI (GINI index), are statistically insignificant.

4. Conclusion

From the analysis based on my results, it can be concluded that several demographic factors, such as HDI, life expectancy at birth, labor force participation rate, urban population growth, and fertility rate, have a significant impact on economic productivity in different countries. Additionally, per capita income, inflation, and public spending on pensions also play a significant role in economic productivity. Apart from the per capita income which was negatively correlated with growth according to the results I had, everything else seems to be in line with previous research and economic theory.

However, it is important to note that the relationship between some of these factors and economic productivity may not be straightforward, and more in-depth research is required to establish a causal relationship. Overall, the findings suggest that policymakers need to consider all demographic factors when formulating economic policies and strategies to enhance productivity in different countries. It is a multifaceted problem, and a policy aiming to change just one or two demographics will not suffice. A lot of in-depth research must still be done, before making policies so they can be backed up by empirical evidence.

Please find the appendix in a separate file where all the details on data sources and analysis performed on STATA 17.0 are available.

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